

Supplementary Material:

Insulin resistance and CGM-derived parameters in people with type 1 diabetes: are they associated?

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Table 1 suppl. Demographic characteristics of the study population and by eGDR categories

Characteristics	Mean (SD), Median (25-75th percentiles), no (%)				p-value
	Total study population	eGDR tertile 1 (9.2 – 12.1 mg/kg/min)	eGDR tertile 2 (6.1 – 9.1 mg/kg/min)	eGDR tertile 3 (1.1 – 6.0 mg/kg/min)	
<i>n</i>	287	96	95	96	
<i>Retinopathy (n, %)</i>	120 (41)	21 (22)	38 (40)	61 (64)	<0.001
<i>Polyneuropathy (n, %)</i>	46 (16)	6 (6)	9 (9)	31 (32)	<0.001
<i>Ischemic cardiovascular disease (n, %)</i>	20 (7)	1 (1)	5 (5)	14 (15)	<0.001
<i>Peripheral vascular disease (n, %)</i>	12 (4)	0	3 (3)	9 (9)	0.001
<i>Cerebrovascular disease (CVA of TIA) (n, %)</i>	5 (2)	0	1 (1)	4 (4)	0.048
<i>Microalbuminuria (n, %)</i>	57 (20)	9 (9)	15 (16)	33 (34)	<0.001
<i>Renal Failure (n, %)</i>	35 (12)	3 (3)	11 (12)	21 (22)	<0.001

estimated glucose disposal rate (eGDR)

The cohort was divided in tertiles based on the eGDR. Chi-squared statistics were used for categorical variables to compare the tertiles. A low eGDR (indicating a higher level of insulin resistance) is associated with the presence of metabolic syndrome, and a higher prevalence of nephropathy, retinopathy and cardiovascular disease, and this irrespective of HbA1c levels ¹⁻⁴, as mentioned in our manuscript. Half of our study population already developed micro- and/or macrovascular complications. Our manuscript confirms that those with the lowest eGDR (and thus being the most insulin resistant) have more complications

Table 2 suppl. Linear regression model for Time in range and Time above range.

	TIR		TAR	
	Coefficient (SE)	p-value	Coefficient (SE)	p-value
Age	0.003 (0.001)	< 0.001	-0.003 (0.001)	< 0.001
Gender (F)	-0.020 (0.017)	0.24	0.048 (0.018)	0.008
Diabetes duration	0.005 (0.002)	0.007	-0.005 (0.002)	0.005
Smoking	-0.012 (0.030)	0.69	-0.001 (0.032)	0.98
Alcohol Intake	0.017 (0.018)	0.34	-0.018 (0.019)	0.35
eGDR	0.037 (0.008)	< 0.001	-0.041 (0.008)	< 0.001
eGDR x Diabetes duration	-0.001 (0.0002)	0.001	0.001 (0.0003)	0.005

estimated glucose disposal rate (eGDR), time in range (TIR), time above range (TAR), standard error (SE)

Interactions between eGDR and each of the confounders were added to the model to check for effect modification. An interaction was found between eGDR and diabetes duration in all analysis with TIR and TAR (linear, binary logistic and ordinal logistic regression). The association between TIR/TAR and eGDR became weaker the longer one had diabetes. All coefficients of the linear regression with TIR and TAR are shown in Supplemental Table 2. No effect modification was found in analysis with TBR or CV.

References

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